

Survey about Participation Platforms in Smart Cities destined to Citizens

Q1

Have you ever heard of the term 'citizen participation'?

(This is the active participation of citizens in public matters. A citizen is then expected to think actively about public decisions to be made)

- Yes, I've heard of it
 - No, never heard of it
-

Q2

Have you ever heard of the term 'participation platform'?

(These are online platforms who enable citizens to introduce new ideas and vote on ideas by other citizens)

- Yes, I've heard of it
 - No, never heard of it
-

Q3

Several of these platforms/movements exist to enable participation for citizens.

From which of the following platforms/movements have you heard before?

(multiple answers possible)

- CitizenLab
- Fluicity
- Createlli
- Youth4Climate
- Yellow vests Movement
- None of the above

End of Block: Platform Knowledge/Awareness

Start of Block: General Platform Questions

We will now ask some general questions about this type of platforms we are researching.

Q4

Which of the following features of such a platform seem important to you?

	Not Important	Less Important	Important	Very Important	
The platform is easy to use (user friendly)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Q5 Do you have any other ideas for important
The platform is often mentioned in media through marketing (promotion)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
The platform is easy and fast to find online (accessible)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Citizens from every age group, education... are active on the platform (representative)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
The ideas from the platform are considered and used by the (local) government	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
The ideas on the platform are anonymous (privacy/anonymity)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
The same ideas are grouped for a comprehensive overview on the platform	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
The platform offers a safe connection for the users (no chance of hacking)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
The platform offers free access for the users	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

features of such online platforms?

End of Block: General Platform Questions

Start of Block: Motivation/restriction of usage

Q6

Why would you potentially use such platforms in the future?

- It would enlarge the mutual trust between me and the government
 - I feel that my ideas would be processed and considered by the (local) government
 - To get an explanation on why my idea can/cannot be realized
 - To minimize the distance between me and the government
 - It is my duty as a citizen
 - Other _____
 - None of the above
-

Q7

What would hinder you from using such platforms in the future?

- I do not trust the government
- My ideas will not be processed or considered
- The government does not pay attention to these platforms
- It is the task of the government to come up with good ideas
- Other _____
- None of the above

End of Block: Motivation/restriction of usage

Start of Block: Culture

You have reached the last part of our survey. Please fill in these final questions about yourself.

Q8

How long are you active on social media per day? (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn...)

- More than 3 hours
 - Between 2-3 hours
 - Between 1-2 hours
 - Less than 1 hour
 - I am not active on social media
-

Q9

How would you describe your general interest in politics? (Privacy assured)

- Extremely Interested
 - Very Interested
 - Moderately Interested
 - Little Interest
 - Not Interested
-

Q10

Are you satisfied with the current political climate in your country? (Privacy assured)

- Extremely Satisfied
 - Very Satisfied
 - Moderately Satisfied
 - Little Satisfied
 - Not Satisfied
-

Q11

How would you describe your political orientation? (Not mandatory, privacy assured)

- I prefer not to answer this question
- Liberal Left
- Nationalistic Left
- Central
- Liberal Right
- Nationalistic Right

End of Block: Culture

Start of Block: General Personal Questions

Q12

What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- X

Q13

To which age group do you belong?

- Younger than 18
 - 18-34 years old
 - 35-50 years old
 - 51-64 years old
 - Older than 64
-

Q14

What is your highest completed education?

- None
 - Primary
 - High School
 - Higher Education (college or university)
 - PhD
-

Q15

What is your nationality?

- Belgian
- Other _____

End of Block: General Personal Questions

We thank you for your time spent taking this survey.
Your response has been recorded.